

POETIC ORNITHONYMY IN ENGLISH FOLKLORE AND TURKOLOGY.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ingliz filologiyasida mifologik ornitonimiyani o'rganish haqida so'z yuritiladi. Jumladan, o'zbek va ingliz folklorida ertaklarda qushlar obrazining o'xshash va farqli jihatlari tahlilga tortilgan. Shuningdek, ajdaho va Oltoy turklarining mifologik qushlari haqida fikrlar bildirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ajdaho, mifologik qushlar, qora qush, oq qarg'a, o'zbek va ingliz folklori, Konrul (afsonaviy burgut).

Annotation

This article discusses the study of mythological ornithonymy in English philology. In particular, similar and different aspects of the image of birds in fairy tales are analyzed in Uzbek and English folklore. There are also stories about dragons and mythological birds of the Altai Turks.

Key words: dragon, mythological birds, black bird, white crow, Uzbek and English folklore, Konrul (legendary eagle).

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается изучение мифологической орнитонимии в английской филологии. В частности, анализируются схожие и разные стороны образа птиц в сказках в узбекском и английском фольклоре. Есть также рассказы о драконах и мифологических птицах алтайских тюрков.

Ключевые слова: дракон, мифологические птицы, черная птица, белая ворона, узбекский и английский фольклор, Конрул (легендарный орел).

A number of scholars have made significant contributions to the study of mythological ornithonymy in English philology. These studies were often conducted in the fields of folklore, mythology and literary studies. For example, J.R.R. Tolkien's essay "On Fairy-Stories" talks about the nature and importance of myth and fantasy, including mythological creatures such as birds. This work is aimed at a comprehensive analysis of the genre of fairy tales and their importance, in which the author studies the nature, origin and functions of fairy tales from a literary and psychological point of view. Its materials are important in studying the place of mythical ornithonymy in the fields of literature, psychology and cultural studies. J. Tolkien said that a fairy tale helps readers to see reality clearly by demystifying everyday things and experiences, and at the same time renews their sense of wonder. And the world of birds has a big role in this. Eucatastrophe in fairy tales - in a sudden, joyful turn of events, bird symbols occupy one of the leading places. According to the scientist, the cognitive and emotional participation of the image of birds in fairy tales is also unique. They encourage mental skills by challenging students to suspend disbelief and explore hypothetical scenarios. Also, the role of birds in the emergence of cultural and moral criteria is also shown through fairy tales. Ornithonym has a great role in the

fact that fairy tales more accurately reflect cultural values and norms, and serve as a tool for passing down folk wisdom to generations. In short, J. Tolkien's work "On Fairy Tales" combines a multifaceted study of the fairy tale genre, literary analysis, psychological concepts and cultural criticism, in which ornithonyms served as an important tool in the study of the taxonomy, functions, origin and influence of fairy tales.

English folklore specialist Jacqueline Simpson has special works on mythological creatures, including birds. For example, his book *Dragons of Britain* covers a number of mythological birds and other creatures from English folklore. In particular, his research on dragons as hybrid creatures deserves attention. In many mythological traditions, dragons often have bird-like characteristics, such as wings and the ability to fly. This hybrid nature emphasizes the harmony of the earth and air domains, signifying power and transcendence. From an evolutionary perspective, the combination of avian and reptilian features in dragons can be seen as a reflection of ancient human attempts to understand and mythologize the natural world based on the observable characteristics of existing animals. Birds in dragon legends often represent vigilance and protection. For example, in English folklore, dragons with bird-like qualities are seen as guardians of treasures or sacred places. The wings, feathers, and good eyesight of mythical birds are often attributed to dragons, emphasizing their role as powerful and vigilant protectors. The scientist also focuses on the physiological characteristics of dragons, typical of birds. In particular, dragons have Phoenix-like features. They embody the themes of resurrection and immortality. This connects dragons with cycles of death and rebirth, common motifs in mythological plots. There are also signs of a dragon and a crow. Known for their intelligence and prophetic abilities, ravens are sometimes associated with dragons. This connection emphasizes the wisdom of dragons and their role as messengers of destiny. At the same time, the scientist pays attention to the psychological interpretation of ornithonym in folklore. Because bird-like dragons are seen as archetypes of transformation and transcendence, their ability to soar into the sky reflects man's quest for spiritual and spiritual ascension. Another aspect of the matter is related to the heraldic (symbolic) and iconographical aspects of the relationship between birds and dragons. In British heraldry, dragons and bird-like creatures often represent nobility, courage and guardianship. The addition of avian features to dragons adds to their majestic and terrifying appearance. Legends and fairy tales often depict dragons with avian characteristics, reinforcing their otherworldly and supernatural qualities. These serve as a moral and educational allegory embodying cultural values. Jacqueline Simpson's "Dragons of Britain" is at the center of attention in world folklore as a special work that explores the complex relationship between birds and dragons in British mythology. The book "Turkish Mythology" is a work that deeply explores myths and characters based on the historical and cultural origins of Turks (in most cases, all Turkic peoples). The belief systems, rituals, mythological figures and epics of the Turkic peoples are detailed in this book. In particular, shamanism, which forms the basis of Turkish mythology, includes rituals and beliefs aimed at communicating with nature and spirits. Shamans play an important role in communities as performers of these rituals. Elements of nature such as mountains, rivers, and trees are considered auspicious places in Turkish mythology, and rituals held in these places strengthen the connection between nature and man. The book is an important resource for preserving and conveying the cultural heritage of the Turkic peoples. Mythological stories reflect the common memory and cultural identity of Turkish society. The book examines the ritual and belief systems of the Turks

and analyzes the impact of these systems on social and individual identities. B. Ozel's book "Turkish Mythology" contains many interesting facts about the place of birds in the spiritual life of Turkic peoples. According to the scientist, "modern shaman's clothes have degenerated. The oldest and original shaman's clothes were clothes imitating the shapes of birds or animals. The shaman who wore it wanted to show that he was (their) ancestor and that he could take the form of that bird whenever he wanted. This change of form is called metamorphosis in mythological studies. And the Turks used the word "to put on a robe" as an equivalent of this expression. In the Bektashis, this situation is interpreted as "with love to the world of meaning". B. Ozel notes in the work "Viloyatnoma" of the famous Turkish mystic A. Gulpnarli that Ahmad Yassavi was based on the movements of the crane in the sky meetings. Also, B. Seyidoglu's work entitled "Turkish Mythological System" is an important source that researches the structure, main elements and tasks of the mythology of the Turkic peoples with a scientific approach. In this book, the origins of Turkish mythology, gods, creatures, heroes and rituals are discussed in detail, and a significant part of them is connected with ornithonyms. In particular, how the origin and historical development of the mythology of the Turkic peoples was formed in the vast area from Central Asia to Anatolia, and how the interactions with different cultures are reflected in the mythology in this process is also addressed by the example of ornithonyms. How mythological elements change and develop over time is related to the socio-cultural dynamics of societies. In particular, the impact of the nomadic lifestyle and conversion to Islam on the mythological structure is discussed. Also, in the book "Mythological stories of Altai Turks" by Hakan Kirimli, there is a comprehensive study of the mythological birds of Altai Turks. These studies discuss the symbolic meanings and functions of bird figures, which have an important place in the cultural and mythological structure of the Altai Turks. The book notes that in his mythological stories, birds are usually associated with sacred and supernatural powers. Birds are depicted in connection with heavenly beings, gods and mythical heroes. In Altai mythology, bird species are usually symbols of life, wisdom and powers. Mythical birds play a special role as representatives of the forces of good and evil. For example, "Al raven" (White crow), "Black bird" and other creatures that lift the souls of the dead during the transition to the afterlife are depicted. The mythological bird figures of these peoples were influenced by other cultures of Central Asia and other mythological traditions in the vast geography of the Turkic peoples. These bird figures appear as a reflection of social values, beliefs and rituals. The book emphasizes that birds are connected with creation, heroism, and sacred duty in mythological stories. The perception of birds as carriers of heavenly messages or signs of the gods emphasizes the importance of these creatures in myths. In the book "Türk Halk Edebiyatında Kush Motifleri" ("Bird Motifs in Turkish Folk Literature") by Ismail Avji, you can find a lot of relevant information. Avji's book focuses on the image of birds in Turkish folk literature, including myths and legends. It analyzes various bird symbols, their symbolic meanings, and their appearance in folk tales and poetry. It provides insight into how mythical birds have been depicted in Turkish literature over time. In particular, Conrul (the mythical eagle) is often associated with strength, power and divine protection. It appears as a symbol of courage and guidance in many Turkish heroic epics and narratives. R. Octan's book "Turkish mythology and shamanism" provides extensive information about Turkish mythology and shamanism. The book describes in detail the place of shamanism in Turkish culture and the connection of this belief system with mythological elements. Looking at the relationship between Turkish mythology and shamanism,

R. Octan examines the influence of shamanism in Turkish society and how this belief system is connected with myths. Shamanism is distinguished by its relationship with nature, interaction with spirits, and traditional rituals. Shamans are described as both religious leaders and mythological characters, and the roles of these characters in mythological narratives are explained in detail. R. Octan examines the rituals performed by shamans and their connection with mythological narratives. It focuses on how shamanic rituals and spiritual practices relate to mythological stories. These rituals often aim to communicate with supernatural forces. The book examines the main themes and symbols in Turkish mythology and explains the influence of shamanism on these themes. In particular, shamanic rites talk about the use of mythological elements such as natural elements, animal figures, cosmic structures. The book explains that birds are associated with spiritual and supernatural forces in shamanistic beliefs. Shamans see birds as carriers of divine messages in the spiritual world. Birds are believed to act as a bridge between heaven and earth. It seems that summarizing the work done on the topic in English philology and Tokology serves to clarify a number of common aspects of the issue of poetic ornithonyms.

USED LITERATURE:

1. J.R.R. Tolkien, *The Monsters and the Critics and Other Essays*,
2. ed. by Christopher Tolkien (London: Harper/Collins, 2006), pp. 109 – 161 (p. 146)
3. Р.Р. Толкин. О волшебных сказках//Чудовища и критики и другие статьи. – М.: Elsewhere, 2006;
4. пер. С. Лихачевой
- 5 <https://wikipedia.net/ru/Eucatastrophe>
6. <https://e-kitapindir.com/turk-mitolojisi-pdf-indir.html>